

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF RESEARCH OF TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEM UNITS

Makhmudova Nilufarkhan Tolkinjan kizi

teacher of the Uzbek language department (PhD) of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Juraeva Ramziya Abdurahimovna

Senior Lecturer of the Uzbek Language Department (PhD) of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Nasirov Muslimbek Makhsutali ogli

Lecturer at Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Toshxujaeva Shoiraxon Ganievna

Senior Lecturer of the Uzbek Language Department (PhD) of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation. The article deals with modern views on terms and terminology in linguistics, modern approaches based on traditional, system-structural, anthropocentric principles in the study of the modern terminological system.

Key words and phrases: term, term system, terminology, traditional, system-structural, anthropocentric principles, telecommunications, telephone terms.

New views that are being formed today in world linguistics have created the need to work on the basis of modern research methods in the study of the terminological system of a language. At the same time, linguistic anthropocentrism, recognized as a new paradigm in world linguistics, has introduced fundamental qualitative changes in the field of terminology, reflecting the progress of science. Today we live in the world of information societies, in a society where the increasingly developing processes of globalization, information, communication and Internet technologies, and intellectual development play a decisive role. In the XXI century, which is considered the century of science and technology, in our country, as well as throughout the world, the need for a rapid exchange of information is growing. For this reason, a number of legal documents were adopted aimed at comprehensive support of the information technology industry. This led to the formation of a new terminological system related to information and communication in all language systems, including the Uzbek language system.

When studying information and communication terms in world linguistics, existing types of analysis in traditional and system-structural linguistics are used, language units are studied on the basis of an anthropocentric approach - in linguocognitive, linguoculturological, sociolinguistic aspects. Particular attention is paid to the integral aspects of changing a particular terminological system with the development of society.

It is known that the concept of terminology and the term have many definitions in dictionaries and scientific literature. Nevertheless, as Professor N. Makhmudov notes, “it should be noted with regret that neither in Uzbek linguistics, nor in other linguistics of the world, even a single definition of the term “ term ”was formed” [14,129].

In the definitions of terms and terminology in the scientific literature, one can see that a certain facet of the essence of these two concepts is revealed.

The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language notes that terminology is a “set of terms” and special attention is paid to the object of its study: “**Terminology** [Latin *terminus* - limit + Greek *logos* - science, teaching]

1. A set of terms used in the field of science, technology, profession. *Technical terminology. military terminology. Scientific terminology. Terminology of the Uzbek language.*
2. A field of linguistics dealing with the study and regulation of terms. *Terminologist. Terminology section*”[20,247].

The fact that terminology is a collection of terms, a system of terms, is reflected in other definitions [21,104]. It is worth saying that some definitions of the term focus on the belonging of the term to a certain semantic field: “Terms make up most of the vocabulary of the common language and exist within the terminological field, within which the term has all the features that describe it. This area is artificially demarcated and deliberately protected from the penetration of unrelated elements, since belonging to a certain area is the most important feature that distinguishes words-terms from ordinary words” [17,58].

From the analyzed scientific definitions it can be seen that in our linguistics the recognition of terminology as a set of terms representing a system of concepts of a particular science and as a branch of linguistics has stalled. The units of the terminological system are lexical units formed directly in the human mind and created for a specific purpose. Development, progress and renewal in any field serve to enrich scientific terms.

Taking into account that the level of knowledge of terms and problems of terminology in the world and Uzbek linguistics was covered in detail in previous works, we considered it necessary to talk about new approaches to the terminological system in the study.

It is noted in the scientific literature that research is being carried out in a number of priority areas in the field of terminology today in world linguistics. These are: lexico-semantic study of terms, their study in a textual environment; linguo-poetic and methodological features of terms, linguo-culturological aspects of terms; the possibility of interstylization of scientific terms, semasiological and lexicographic interpretation of terms; study of terms in the anthropocentric approach, comparative and cross analysis of terms, and others [10,56].

During the years of independence, traditional, system-structural, anthropocentric principles of language learning were simultaneously used. The introduction of an anthropocentric approach to language has led to a number of new studies in the field of terminology. Now the terms are studied on the basis of field theory, as well as the principles of analysis in traditional linguistics. This led to the definition of the systemic characteristics of many terminological systems.

One of the important features of the Uzbek terminology of the new century is the anthropocentric approach to term systems. The introduction of the anthropocentric approach to linguistics has given rise to a number of new studies in the field of terminology. Currently, in Uzbek linguistics, terms are widely approached from a cognitive, linguistic and cultural point of view. This led to the formation and consolidation in our linguistics of theoretical views on the status of terms as a national-cultural concept, linguocultural unity, reflecting the national thought and practice of the people.

In world linguistics, the implementation of research on terminology from the point of view of the cognitive approach [5] served as a motive for creating works in this direction in Uzbek linguistics [6,10]. New theoretical views have been formed about the importance of the linguocognitive approach in describing terminological systems, about the fact that terminology is associated with concepts and concepts that reflect the worldview, and that it is a product of human cognitive activity.

In the studies of B. Mirsanov, who worked on the topic of secondary naming in the Uzbek language and their motivation, an associative approach to terms is noticeable [15]. In Uzbek linguistics, in a later period, interest in the study of terms in a comparative aspect increased. The study of the terminological systems of the Uzbek language in comparison with the terminological systems of related and unrelated languages served to discover new aspects of the nature of our language [8]. A number of studies in the field of telecommunications have been carried out in world linguistics. In particular, the Russian scientist A. V. Ivkina revealed the issues of translating terms into English, French and Russian using the example of telecommunication terms. And Krupeneva V.P. studied the terms of the user interface of networks and a set of screen states using the example of the English language [13].

Some research is focused on the description and social impact of global communications networks, with particular attention to the relations of the telecommunications industry between the countries of the world [2,21].

In some works, using the Twitter site as an example, the increasing globalization in the era of digital communications, the assimilation of English-language telecommunication terms by other languages through social networks and the creation of their alternatives are highlighted [3].

It is known that in the era of globalization, the influence of the English language on other languages is increasing. A study by H. A. Altaher examines Arabic computer terms that have been adopted in English. In the course of studying the computer terminology of this language, the researcher found out that most of the field terms in this language came from the English language, analyzed the issues of ambiguity in the scope of their application and replacement with equivalents [1].

In his scientific work at Stafford University (Great Britain), Donal Lunch, along with some principles of traditional approaches in English linguistics, puts forward the view that studying in isolation from the text prevents an adequate assessment of the difference between words and terms, and recommends an approach to terminology taking into account communication processes [14].

It should be noted that telecommunication terms were not the subject of special monographic studies in Uzbek linguistics. A partial answer to this question is given by D. Kadyrbekova's study in a comparative typological aspect. As a work directly related to our topic, we can note the study of D. Saidkadirova, who conducted a linguistic study of Internet terms in English and Uzbek [18]. Also, Kh. Narkhodjaeva partially drew attention to the terms of information technology in explaining the linguistic features of the process of the meaning of terms in the Uzbek language [16].

Recognizing that the above studies have made a certain contribution to the study of telecommunication terms in the Uzbek language, it cannot be said that this rapidly developing area, in particular, the study of the terms of telephone networks, has been studied enough in Uzbek linguistics. It should be said that in the scientific literature and terminological dictionaries created to date in the field of information and communication, a special place is occupied by terms composed of commonly used words. The study of their semantic features with the help of the context, understanding their differences from commonly used words puts on the agenda the creation of special scientific research. This requires a special study of the semantic and compositional features of telecommunication terms that have acquired a new meaning in our language. At the moment, the analysis of the above lexemes shows that most of the lexemes that have become terms are widely used, along with the Uzbek version, and belong to the assimilated layer. For example: *network, text, address, database, link, label (link)*.

It should be noted that telecommunications terminology is characterized by such features as the rapid enrichment of vocabulary, a high level of mastery of words, active familiarity with commonly used words, polysemy of types and varieties. To date, most telecommunications terms that have entered the broad consumer sphere and are used with high frequency, in particular, the terms of the telephone network, are not reflected in dictionaries representing the vocabulary of the Uzbek language (for example, *account, domain, web conference, web browser, web design...*), and the semantic content of some of them does not contain a comment that should be described as a telecommunication term: *banner, byte, bit, command, virtual, program, driver, search, privilege, frame, key, directory, keylogger, cache, cluster, code, cart, panel, password, post, mail, profile, cart, slide, network* and so on.

These facts confirm that one of the important tasks of Uzbek linguistics is the study of the processes of terminization taking place in our language, emerging term neologisms, as well as lexical units that are assimilated at a rapid pace not only in the case of telecommunications, but also in the case of other terminological systems, and determining the status of new terms in the vocabulary of our language.

It is known that the term "*telecommunication*" comes from the Greek words "*tele*", which means *far*, and the Latin word "*communicatio*", which means *communication*, "transmission of information over long distances". But today the term is used in a broad sense. In particular, describing telecommunications, I. Gusev says that "telecommunications is understood as a set of means of communication that serve to transmit information over a certain distance, such means

include sound, signal, text, symbol, written image, cable, optical, radio and others claim that it is transmitted through electromagnetic devices [9].

Telecommunications is also described in scientific literature as a process of data transmission and storage. According to Sh. Saidova, telecommunications is a process of remote transmission, reception and processing of a data stream using electronic, electromagnetic, network, computer and information carriers, through which useful results are achieved and the requirement to transmit and receive data through special software and technical means are worked out [19,14].

It is known that telecommunications is a process carried out using wire, radio, optical or other electromagnetic systems, a set of technical means designed to transmit one or more types, including telephone, telegraph, facsimile information and other documentary messages, machine-to-machine information exchange, television and radio broadcasts.

Based on the available findings, it can be said that the field of telecommunications today mainly includes interconnected telephone networks, radio communications, television and computer communication systems. In scientific sources, a different classification of networks of the telecommunications industry is noticeable. For example, the Russian scientist V. Krupenev singled out the following networks in telecommunications:

1. Telegraph system. 2. Telephone system. 3. TV system. 4. Radio transmission system. 5. Postal system. 6. Global information systems (Internet) or national data transmission systems [13].

Also, when studying telecommunication terminology in linguistics, special attention is paid to the periodization of the formation and development of this area. In particular, A. Ivkina studied the terminological system of the industry, divided into the following periods:

1. Post (XIII century). 2. Telegraphy (late 18th century). 3. Telephony (late 19th century). 4. Radio broadcast (first quarter of the 19th century). 5. Television (XX century). 6. Information exchange (70s of the XX century) [11].

The terms related to the telecommunications terminology system can be divided into the following 4 groups depending on their current activities and the sectors they cover:

1. Terms of the telephone network (telephony). 2. Terms of the radio network. 3. TV network terms. 4. Computer technology terms.

It is known that telegraph communications, along with the telephone network, were effectively used to transmit information over long distances. But in today's era of technical and technological progress, new generations of communication have appeared, and modern mobile phones have taken their place. Also, as a result of the introduction of new communication technologies, the scope of telephony has expanded due to the Internet service and mobile communications, that is, videoconferencing.

Telecommunication terminological system as an independent system has the following characteristics:

1. Telecommunication terminology consists of the terms of telephone, radio communication, television, computer technology and has a common feature in that it serves to create a communicative environment between communicants and exchange information.
2. The emergence of telecommunications terms is closely related to the results of technical and technological development in the main cases, which requires that this terminological system has the characteristics of an open system that quickly accepts new terms related to this area.
3. The units of the telecommunications terminology system are often hierarchically related to each other.
4. The telecommunication terminological system has the peculiarity of division into thematic groups, lexico-semantic series, division into components.

"User terminals" of the telephone network (as a rule, telephone equipment); communication line (subscriber and connecting lines); "Switching center and telephone exchanges" [22] have their own terminological units. In telecommunications, a special place is occupied by a *mobile communication* network that performs the service of transmitting voice, text, graphic data to a specific address or territory through wireless terminals. The most common type of *mobile communication* is cellular communication. This communication system is built on the basis of multi-zone, that is, the maintenance of areas divided into cells. The sources note that these zones are so named because they form an image similar to the honeycombs of a beehive in the plan of the city [23]. Cellular communication is a type of mobile radio communication that provides all types of telephone services. One of the organizers of cellular communications are cell phones, which perform the function of transmitting all information without wires by means of electromagnetic waves in a mobile communication system.

In telecommunications, the mobile telephone system, the principles of its operation, the technology for the creation, development and use of technical means that provide telephone communications, the transmission of information in speech through this type of communication, its quality, scientific and technical fields are called *telephony*. The purpose of the study is to study the terms of this communication system of telecommunications.

It is known that the term "telephony" comes from the Greek words τῆλε + φωνή, meaning "distance" + "voice, sound". Telephony, as an independent telecommunications communication network, performs the tasks of organizing telephone communications, sending faxes, real-time modem connections in local areas, their internal zones, as well as between cities and nations [13]. In connection with this task, many terms appeared in the terminology of the region.

In the scientific literature, different definitions of *terms* and *terminology* are given, and each definition reveals a certain aspect of the essence of these two concepts. In particular, these definitions emphasize that terminology is a set of terms, a system of terms, a section of linguistics that studies terms. During the years of independence, traditional, system-structural, anthropocentric principles of language learning were simultaneously used. During this period, terms were also studied on the basis of field theory. This led to the definition of the systemic characteristics of many terminological systems. One of the important features of the Uzbek

terminology of the new century is the anthropocentric approach to term systems. As a result of the approach to terms in cognitive, linguistic and cultural aspects, theoretical views have been established in our linguistics that these units have the status of a national-cultural concept, a linguo-cultural unit, reflect national thinking and confirmed practical views. An important point of view was put forward that the study of terms not only within the sentence, but also within the text will serve to identify the features of their speech styles. Also in a later period, interest in the study of terms in a comparative aspect increased. A number of studies in the field of telecommunications in world linguistics have been carried out. In Uzbek linguistics, this system was mainly the object of comparative typological research. Scientific and technological progress and growing international economic cooperation bring a number of updates to the telecommunications terminology system. From this point of view, in our linguistics there is a need to study the current state of this system, in particular, the field of telephony, its development trends, and its relationship with the literary language. Telecommunication is a process carried out using radio, optical or other electromagnetic systems, a set of technical means for transmitting telephone, telegraph, facsimile messages and other documentary messages, machine-to-machine exchange of information, television and radio broadcasts. The terms related to the telecommunications terminology system can be divided into the following types according to the nature of their activities and what networks they cover today: telephone network (telephony) terms, radio network terms, telecommunication network terms, computer technology terms. All of the above is the basis for further research.

REFERENCES:

1. Altaher A.H. Lexical borrowing (ta'rib) in Arabic computing terminology: issues and strategies—The university of Durham. Great Britain, 2015.
2. Choi Young *Global networks: –The university of Buffalo, Nyu-york, USA, 2003. –B.21.*
3. Gina Caruso. French Language Legislation the Digital Age: The Use of Borrowed English Telecommunication Terms and Their Official French Replacements on Twitter and in the American Foreign Language Classroom. Master's thesis –Minnesota State University, USA, 2012.
4. Lynch Donal. A. *Study of the lexicography of computing and information technology and its practical applications: PhD. –Staffordshire University, 2004.*
5. Neubauer P.B. Towards terminology research as a practical philosophy of information: the terminology of radical constructivism as a case in point. Great Britain, The university of Salford, 2014.
6. Abdirasheva A. *Zamonaviy turk tilidagi iqtisodiy terminlarning lingvokognitiv tahlili: Filol. fan. bo'yicha falsafa d-ri (PhD) diss. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2019. –B.10.*
7. Abdullaeva Sh.N. *G'aznachilik sohasida qo'llanadigan moliyaviy-iqtisodiy terminlarning chog'ishtirma tadqiqi (ingliz, rus, o'zbek tillari misolida):. Filol.fan. d-ri (PhD) diss. – Toshkent, 2018. – B.30.*

8. Ahmedov O.S. *Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida soliq-bojxona terminlarining lingvistik tahlili va tarjima muammolari: Filol. fan. d-ri. ... diss. – Toshkent, 2016. – 255 b;*
9. Gusev I.V. Ponyatie telekommunikatsiy i ix rol v sovremennom mire // [https://sibac.info/archive/technic/4\(40\).pdf](https://sibac.info/archive/technic/4(40).pdf)
10. Jamoliddinova D. *Badiiy matnda terminlarning lingvopoetik va lingvokul'turologik xususiyatlari: Filol. fan. d-ri. diss. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2021. – 56 b.*
11. Ivkina A.V. *Osobennosti obrazovaniya i perevoda terminov v angliyskom, frantsuzskom i russkom yazikax (na materiale predmetnoy oblasti «Telekommunikatsiya» i podoblasti «Telefoniya»): Diss. ... kand. filol. nauk. – Sankt - Peterburg, 2004.*
12. Krupenyova V.P. *Ekrannie termini polzavatel'skogo interfeysa v teoreticheskom prikladnom rassmotrenii: na materiale angliyskogo yazika: Dis. ...kand. filol. nauk. – Smolensk, 2012.*
13. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%A2%D0%B5%D0%BB%D0%B5%D0%84%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%B8%D1%8F> D1%
14. Mahmudov N. *Til tilsimi tadqiqi. – Toshkent: Mumtoz soz, 2017. – B.129.*
15. Mirsanov B. *O'zbek tili terminologiyasida ikkilamchi nomlanishlar va ularning motivlashuvi (o'zbek tili zoonimlari va fitonimlari misolida): Filol. fan. bo'yicha falsafa. d-ri (PhD) diss. – Toshkent, 2019. – 146 b.*
16. Narxodjaeva X. *O'zbek tilidagi jarayon anglatuvchi terminlarning lingvistik xususiyatlari: Filol. fan. bo'yicha falsafa d-ri (PhD) dis. avtoref. – Toshkent, 2017.*
17. Paluanova X.D. *Ingliz, o'zbek, rus va qoraqalpoq tillarida ekologik terminlarning derivatsion-semantik printsiplari: Filol.fan. nomz. dis. – Toshkent, 2016. –B.58.*
18. Saidqodirova D. *Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida internet terminlarining lingvistik tadqiqi: Filol. fan. bo'yicha falsafa d-ri (PhD) dis. avtoref.. – Toshkent, 2018.*
19. Saidova Sh. *Formirovanie i razvitie rinka telekommunikatsionnix uslug v Respublike Tadjikistan (na primere operatorov mobilnoy svyazi): Diss. ...kand. ekonom. nauk. – Dushanbe, 2018. – S.14.*
20. *O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. – Toshkent: “O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2008 – 5 jildli. – 4-jild. – 606 b.*
21. Hojiev A. *Tilshunoslik terminlarining izohli lug'ati. – Toshkent: “O'zbekiston milliy entsiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2002. –B.104.*
22. <http://uz.infocom.uz/2013/07/01/telefon-va-telefon-aloqasining-rivojlanish-tarixi/>
23. https://www.krugosvet.ru/enc/nauka_i_tehnika/tehnologiya_i_promyshlennost/MOBILNAYA_SVYAZ.html